

THE ROLE OF LANGUAGE IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation. This study discusses the importance of understanding culture in intercultural communication. The author identifies the main aspects of intercultural communication and foreign language learning.

Key words: Language, intercultural relations, culture, country, communication.

The importance of language is considered important in strengthening effective intercultural relations. Language is an ability of the human brain. This allows people to understand their own culture and the culture of other countries. Each country has its own culture. When studying abroad, cultural differences can hinder communication. Language helps solve the cultural economy and develops deep perspectives of a foreign state.

Given that culture is an important aspect of interaction and the role of language in the holistic perception of culture, in this article we will consider whether it is necessary to learn a language when studying abroad.

Culture includes beliefs, language, and social habits that define a group. Culture influences how people communicate, perceive each other and relationships that are promoted based on cultural orientation. Culture reflects the identity of the country. Intercultural dialogue involves the exchange of ideas between people of different cultural backgrounds. Language plays a crucial role in intercultural communication.

Language helps to understand the ethnicity of other people and learn how different cultures perceive each other. Thus, language acts as the main vessel through which culture is transmitted. Therefore, based on different points of view, language plays an important role in developing a deep understanding of the country. Thus, language learning becomes a necessity while studying in the country.

Communication skills include active listening, discipline, collaboration, teamwork, oral communication and written communication skills. These skills allow you to adapt your communication to different audiences, solve problems and achieve common goals.

While many societies geographically or historically related to each other have similar cultures, there are others that have completely different cultural characteristics in remote, socially isolated places. For example, some social

groups have learned a language that includes oral and written communication skills, while others have naturally developed their language over millennia. Consequently, the cultural characteristics that affect communication cannot be compared between all cultures.

As already mentioned, cultural differences between communicators can affect their communication exponentially. It is recommended to use what you have learned about cultural differences in communication to increase productivity in an existing job or improve your prospects when looking for a new employment opportunity.

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